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Electroreduction and Coulometric Determination of Europium(III) in Calcium Nitrate Tetrahydrate Melt

C. K. BHASKARE*

Department of Chemistry, Shivaji University,
Kolhapur-416 004

and

K. N. GANAGE

Department of Chemistry, S. S. G. M. College,
Kopergaon-423 601

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It is possible to acquire more information regarding the chemical behaviour of metal ions by changing over from aqueous to non-aqueous or molten salt media. Such information can be acquired in general by applying electrochemical techniques. In recent years, an array of electrochemical methods such as coulometry, amperometry and variations thereof are available to the chemist. Amongst the metal ions the rare earths are less explored.

Europium is unique amongst the rare earths due to its suitable thermal neutron cross-section of 43 000 barn; due to which it is increasingly used at control rod material. Hence, its analytical estimation is also important. Earlier works on europium in non-aqueous¹⁻⁴ and molten salt media^{5,6} have shown that there is need of further work for better understanding of the lower oxidation states.

Much of the work in molten salts is done in eutectic mixtures of alkali metal salts at $\sim 150-250^\circ$. The hydrated metal nitrates also melt over fairly low range of temperatures and hence, we have studied the electrochemistry of reduction of rare earth ions in molten hydrated metal nitrates. This paper presents the study of electroreduction and coulometric generation of europous ions in calcium

nitrate tetrahydrate melt, and subsequent biamperometric titration with dichromate ions at 55° . Simultaneous determination of europium and samarium has also been studied.

Experimental

For polarographic studies a Sargent-Welch XVI recording polarograph was used along with a dropping mercury electrode ($m=19 \text{ mg s}^{-1}$ $t=3 \text{ s}$, $h=60 \text{ cm}$, $A=0.1072 \text{ cm}^2$). For coulometric generation of europous ion a Systronics 621 stabilised DC power supply which gave ripple-free current, was used. A dead-stop titrator fabricated in our laboratory, was used for biamperometric measurements. A jacketed burette and jacketed cells were used in all experiments; constant temperature ($55 \pm 1^\circ$) was maintained by circulation of water from Adept water thermostat. A double walled, water-jacketed borosilicate glass cell was used for polarographic measurements. A double walled, water-jacketed borosilicate glass cell (Fig 1) was used for both coulometric generation and biamperometric titration. The generating electrodes were

Fig. 1. Coulometric assembly.

of platinum. The anode was placed in a fritted glass compartment, whereas the cathode was in the outer compartment. Two indicator electrodes of platinum wire, were used in the biamperometric end-point detection. An externally driven stirrer was used for proper stirring of the viscous calcium nitrate tetrahydrate melt.

Calcium nitrate tetrahydrate and potassium dichromate were of A.R. grade, and europium nitrate was prepared from europium oxide (Indian Rare Earths) by dissolution in 4 M nitric acid and by slow evaporation.

Europium nitrate (1.160 g) was dissolved and diluted with calcium nitrate tetrahydrate melt. The contents of the flask were shaken to attain homogeneity and then the solution was standardised for europium content⁷. The stock and the diluted solutions (5 mg Eu/ml) were kept in a thermostat. $K_2Cr_2O_7$ (0.049 g) was dissolved in calcium nitrate tetrahydrate melt (100 ml). The solution (0.00167M) was kept in a thermostat at $55 \pm 1^\circ$.

Procedure : The polarograms run with varying concentrations of europium are shown in Fig. 2. The solubility of the oxygen in the melt is negligible⁸ and hence no special precautions were taken to exclude air from the system, except that the cell was covered with a rubber cork with a small hole. By passing a constant current of 10 mA over a known interval of time, a known amount of Eu^{III} ions was converted to Eu^{II} state. The contents of the outer part of the cell were titrated amperometrically or biamperometrically. The experiment

Fig. 2. Current-voltage dc polarograms for reduction in calcium nitrate tetrahydrate melt : (I, II, III) Eu^{III} , and (IV) $Cr_2O_7^{2-}$.

was repeated by passing the same constant current for varying durations until a constant titration reading was obtained. The results gave an L-shaped biamperometric curve for 0.003 g of Eu^{III} ion (Fig. 6). The complete conversion of Eu^{III} to Eu^{II} is indicated by the constancy of readings. The results of amperometric titrations are similar and are not given separately. The amount of Eu^{III} was determined from the dichromate consumed.

Results and Discussion

The systems studied presented well defined polarograms without peaks. Fig. 3 shows the variation of limiting current with the concentration of europium; the straight line passing through the origin indicates that the reaction is diffusion-controlled. The polarographic reduction of Eu^{III} gave a reversible wave at -0.71 V. The plotting of $\log(i/i_a - i)$ vs potential (Fig. 4) yielded a straight

line with a reciprocal of slopes as 0.068, showing that a reversible single-electron reduction process is involved. The diffusion coefficient of europium in this melt is $0.728 \times 10^{-7} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$.

Fig. 3. Variation of current with concentration.

Fig. 4. Heyrovsky-Ilkovic plot of reduction waves of Eu^{III} ; concn. of Eu^{III} ion = $1.00 \times 10^{-4} M$.

Europium is successfully determined by the constant current coulometric technique, followed by biamperometric end-point detection. The results are tabulated in Table 1. The plot of biamperometric

TABLE 1—BIAMPEROMETRIC DETERMINATION OF Eu^{III}

Eu^{III} taken mg	Eu^{III} found mg	Std. deviation $n=5$
1.50	1.46	0.002
2.26	2.24	0.002
3.00	2.98	0.002
4.00	4.01	0.001
4.51	4.50	0.001
5.00	5.02	0.002

metric detection of the redox reaction between Eu^{II} and dichromate ion is L-shaped (Fig. 5). This type of curve is obtained when electroactive material is continually removed by reaction with another electroinactive species. As the medium is highly viscous, satisfactory results are obtained by

keeping the current low and by using efficient stirring. In biamperometric method, a constant potential difference of 100 mV is applied between the two electrodes. From quantity of electric charge in coulombs passed through the cell, the

Fig. 5. Biamperometric titration curve of Eu^{III} ion titrated against $0.00167 M \text{K}_2\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7$ in calcium nitrate tetrahydrate melt.

amount of europous ion obtained by reduction of Eu^{III} was calculated. The 100% agreement between the amount added to the melt and the amount calculated confirms that Eu^{II} formed in electrolysis is not reoxidised to Eu^{III} by the electrolyte. The current was maintained constant at 10 mA because the current values higher than 20 mA lead to the formation of hydrogen gas during electrolysis⁹.

The polarography of europium has been studied by Chapron and Condom¹ in tetrasodium salt of xylenol orange as a ligand and they found that shift in the potential increases with increasing concentration of ligand. Sevryukov and Khasan² studied the effect of pH on the polarographic reduction of Eu^{III} and found two reduction waves. Hush and Dyke³ studied polarographic reduction in DMF and found that the rate of electron transfer is very slow. The polarographic reduction in acetonitrile in presence of halides⁴ showed that the iodide ions are oxidised by Eu^{III} ions, leading to erroneous results. Francini and Martini⁵ studied the polarographic reduction of Eu^{III} in the lithium nitrate sodium nitrate-potassium nitrate eutectic melt but it requires high temperature ($\sim 150-250^\circ$). The electroreduction in calcium nitrate tetrahydrate melt medium offers a reliable laboratory method since it is possible to confine to process to a reversible single electron change. Eventhough the medium is viscous, the rate of change of electron is quite satisfactory. Since the temperature required is quite low compared to the alkali metal halides melt, this medium proves to be better.

In earlier work on coulometric determination of Eu^{III} in methanol by controlled potential technique¹⁰, deaeration of the system was required. Coulometric determination of Eu^{III} in lithium chloride-potassium chloride melt¹¹ by using tungsten electrode, leads to the corrosion of tungsten electrode. In the present system, the europous ion, which is kinetically stable under experimental conditions, is determined by using redox titrimetry. The results are accurate and reproducible.

Fig. 6. Relationship between electrolysis time and dichromate (ml) added in the biamperometric end-point detection of Eu^{III} ion.

From the above discussion, it is clear that this method offers the desired accuracy and precision.

Simultaneous determination of Eu^{III} and Sm^{III} : Europium in the presence of samarium can be titrated by using amperometric end-point detection at -0.80 V . Samarium does not give a reversible wave at this voltage in calcium nitrate tetrahydrate melt. The biamperometric determination will give total amount of europium and samarium in the mixture, while amperometry gives only the amount of europium. The difference accounts for the amount of samarium. The results of such determinations are given in Table 2.

TABLE 2—SIMULTANEOUS DETERMINATION OF Eu^{III} AND Sm^{III} IN A MIXTURE

Europium			Samarium		
taken mg	found mg	St. deviation ($n=5$)	taken mg	found mg	Std. deviation ($n=5$)
1.50	1.48	0.002	1.50	1.46	0.004
2.30	2.31	0.001	2.00	1.97	0.003
3.00	2.99	0.001	1.00	0.95	0.005
4.00	3.98	0.002	2.50	2.47	0.003

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